

Working While Sick: Presenteeism in Israel

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Taub Center for Social Policy Studies in Israel

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Introduction

Presenteeism, according to one widely accepted definition, is the presence of an employee at their workplace while ill (Johns, 2010).¹ Due to a lack of data, the issue of presenteeism in Israel has not yet been examined comprehensively across the entire labor market. Only in the Social Survey 2016 conducted by the Israel Central Bureau of Statistics (CBS) was a question regarding this issue included. Data from this survey indicated that 59% of Israeli workers aged 20 and over reported instances of presenteeism. In a survey conducted among European Union countries during the same period, a similar question was asked, finding that the average rate of presenteeism among workers was 42%

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- 1 Some researchers broaden the definition of presenteeism, describing it as employees who come to work but do not work at full productivity for various reasons, such as poor health, concerns for family members, or distractions — for example, from other workers in the workplace (Schultz et al., 2009). Simpson (1998) discusses competitive presenteeism, a scenario where employees engage in a sort of competition to stay at the office longer (e.g., due to fear of becoming redundant or a desire to stand out for promotion). According to the Academy of the Hebrew Language, presenteeism is defined as “the presence of an employee at work even if they are not performing their job due to illness or other reasons.”

(Schnabel, 2022). In contrast, in the US, two out of every three workers reported presenteeism (Maestas et al., 2021). Another study examining European Union employees found that among workers who reported presenteeism, the average number of days they went to work while ill exceeded seven (Arnold, 2016).

Presenteeism has both health and economic costs. From a health perspective, employees who go to work while ill with contagious diseases risk infecting colleagues, clients, patients, or students, potentially spreading the infection beyond the workplace (Gur-Arie et al., 2021; Widera et al., 2010).² Nevertheless, individuals going to work while ill primarily endanger themselves. Delaying sick leave at an early stage of an illness may lead to more severe illness progression and subsequently increase in medically-related absences (Bergström et al., 2009; Demerouti et al., 2009). On the other hand, going to work with a non-contagious illness, under certain circumstances, allows employees to maintain a professional and social routine, which may even aid in their recovery process (Sanderson & Cocker, 2013).

From an economic perspective, health risk factors among employees lead to costs associated with reduced productivity. These costs arise from both absenteeism and presenteeism. The productivity loss for a workday due to health-related absenteeism is 100%. These losses are relatively easy to quantify since absences are documented and can be calculated based on wages. However, it is much more difficult to estimate the costs arising from presenteeism. These costs embody productivity losses due to slower work pace, professional errors, safety violations, and more (Caverley et al., 2007; Gilbreath & Karimi, 2012; Loepke et al., 2003; Niven & Ciborowska, 2015). In certain cases, presenteeism provides benefits at the individual and organizational level. For instance, individuals with non-contagious illnesses who go to work may be perceived as committed employees, which could enhance their status and future promotion prospects. Presenteeism reduces costs arising from hiring replacement workers and alleviates the workload for other employees (Schnabel, 2022).

2 The effects of presenteeism became much clearer with the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic, during which we learned of cases where symptomatic individuals continued to socialize or come to work, impacting colleagues, students, patients, clients, and others.

In a literature review by Schultz et al. (2009), it was noted that there is no consensus in research on a measurement method that allows the quantification of losses due to presenteeism in financial terms. However, some studies have shown that cumulative costs of presenteeism exceed those of absenteeism (Biron et al., 2006; Hemp, 2004; Medibank, 2011; Parsonage & Saini, 2017). In a study conducted in the United States, employees who worked while ill were asked how much they believed their productivity had decreased. According to respondents, productivity decreased on average by 23% (Maestas et al., 2021). In conclusion, despite the difficulty in measuring the costs of presenteeism, it is an issue that cannot be ignored.

This study is the first attempt to examine the extent of presenteeism in Israel and the factors affecting it. The study is divided into four parts: the first part focuses on the dependent variable, specifically on methodological challenges arising from the wording of the question defining presenteeism; the second part presents a literature review of factors affecting presenteeism; the third part describes the current state of presenteeism in Israel based on the results of a multivariate analysis; and at the end of the article, a brief summary is provided.

Database and dependent variable

Data: This study uses data from the CBS Social Survey that is based on a representative sample of the entire population in Israel. The Social Survey 2016 focused on the working conditions of employees and included a question addressing presenteeism. Unfortunately, this is the only year for which relevant data are available for examining the issue of presenteeism. Additional questions as used in this study are provided in the Appendix. The analysis was limited to employed individuals aged 25–64. The sample size for employed individuals was approximately 3,800 observations, including around 3,200 observations for salaried employees.

This study makes extensive use of subjective data. Generally, researchers who rely on subjective data aim for respondents to be as honest and accurate as possible in their answers. It is known that subjective measures are often influenced by biases, such as social desirability, question wording, and question order, more than behavioral measures (Kristensen & Westergaard-Nielsen, 2007).³ The use of subjective measures may introduce statistical

3 Social desirability bias is where respondents do not report the whole truth because they prefer not to deviate from the norm or want to avoid looking bad relative to others. For example, they may be reluctant to admit to poor behavior or something perceived as a personal failure.

noise as individuals' attitudes and feelings at a given time can be influenced by various events within and outside the workplace. Nonetheless, subjective measures provide a complementary perspective to explain the motivations behind individual behavior. For example, the likelihood of an employee leaving their job is higher among those reporting dissatisfaction at work compared to those who do not report such dissatisfaction. Furthermore, in the field of health specifically, subjective measures predict general health status, longevity, mortality, and cardiovascular diseases (see literature review in Diener & Chan, 2011). Thus, due to the correlation between an individual's feelings and their workplace behavior, the information embedded in subjective data should not be disregarded.

The *dependent variable* is based on the question from the Social Survey: "During the past twelve months, have you worked while being sick? (Responses: Yes, No)." Unfortunately, there is no question regarding the actual number of days the individual went to work while ill.⁴

The phrasing of the Social Survey question raises two main points:

1. The wording of the question presents an interpretive challenge for employees who combine work from home — did these employees physically come to the workplace when they were sick, or did they simply work from home? This distinction is relevant since the arrival of employees with contagious illnesses at their workplace impacts public health. The survey data is from a period preceding the Covid-19 outbreak, and it is known that the percentage of employees who worked from home at that time was relatively low, less than 4% (Madhala & Bental, 2020). Therefore, it can be inferred that the vast majority of respondents to the 2016 survey question intended that they physically went to the workplace while ill. In any case, the analysis excludes individuals who responded that they work from home.
2. Ideally, it would be preferable to compare sick employees who decide to go to work with those who choose to stay home. The responses to the survey question on presenteeism indicate that all employees answered it, meaning

4 In the study by Aronsson et al. (2000), the question on presenteeism was phrased as follows: "Has it happened over the previous 12 months that you have gone to work despite feeling that you really should have taken sick leave due to your state of health?" (Responses: No, never; Yes, once; Yes, 2–5 times; Yes, more than 5 times). See also similar studies with comparable questions and answers: Aronsson & Gustafsson, 2005; Hansen & Andersen, 2008.

that this group also includes individuals who were not sick at all during the year. Including employees who were not sick during the year in the sample undermines the aim to compare sick employees who went to work with other sick individuals who stayed home. The logical step is to examine how many individuals were sick at least once during the year. Unfortunately, the database does not provide data on the number of people who were sick during the year, but this can be roughly estimated. Accordingly, employees who were sick at least once during the past year are defined as those who meet at least one of the following conditions: (1) employees whose health status is generally not very good or not good at all; (2) needed medical treatment; (3) needed prescription medication; (4) reported persistent health issues during the year; (5) reported depression (always or often); (6) reported sleep disturbances due to worries (always or often); (7) reported feeling stressed (always or often); (8) have a severe functional disability;⁵ (9) reported absence for medical reasons; (10) reported presenteeism.

Based on this definition, which includes ten indicators of an individual's health status, it was found that the vast majority of employees aged 25–64 (92%) were sick at least once during the year. This scenario appears realistic; a study covering 188 countries found that only about 4% of people had no illness or injury at all in 2013 (The Lancet, 2015).

The sample used for the analyses later in the study is based on 92% of the employees and salaried workers in the survey who are included in the group of employees who were sick at least once during the year according to the above conditions. As noted, employees who reported working from home were not included in the calculations. Overall, 61% of employees reported working while sick (Figure 1). When limiting the sample to employees who were sick at least once during the year, the data indicate that about two-thirds of employees worked while sick.

5 People with a severe functional disability were defined according to the CBS (2022) definition: "Those who have great difficulty or are unable to perform at least one of the following actions: seeing, hearing, walking or climbing stairs, dressing or bathing, remembering or concentrating." According to this definition, in 2016, about 10% of individuals and about 6% of employed persons aged 25–64 had a severe functional disability.

Figure 1. Extent of presenteeism in Israel among workers aged 25–64, by employee health characteristics, 2016

Note: Excluding employees who work from home. The distribution for salaried employees only is almost identical to that of all workers.

Source: Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Social Survey 2016

Factors influencing presenteeism: Literature review

Health status: The decision to go to work while sick or to stay home depends on an individual's health condition and their ability to manage the illness (for example, with medication). The health risk to colleagues is also a factor when deciding whether to go to work while sick. The literature identifies health conditions contributing to presenteeism, including anxiety, depression, colds, headaches, coughs, allergies, asthma, gastritis, and diabetes (Gosselin et al., 2013; Schultz et al., 2009). In certain health situations, going to work enables an employee to maintain a professional and social routine, which can also aid their recovery (Karanika-Murray & Biron, 2020; Sanderson & Cocker, 2013).

Gender: The literature presents varying evidence regarding gender's impact on presenteeism. Some studies show that presenteeism is more common among women, others find it more prevalent among men, and still others report no significant difference between men and women (Gustafsson Sendén et al., 2016; Webster et al., 2019). Part of the variation in findings may stem from

the fact that these studies examined specific occupations. A separate study, examining 19 European Union countries, found that on average (without controlling for other variables) in most countries, presenteeism rates were higher among women than men, while in other countries, no gender difference was found (Schnabel, 2022).

Certain health issues are more common among women or are unique to them, increasing absenteeism and presenteeism. A study conducted in the United States found that the rate of women suffering from migraines is significantly higher than that of men (Burton et al., 2002). According to the Hadassah website, one in four women suffers from migraines compared to one in 12 men (a threefold difference).⁶ Some studies indicate that menstruation-related symptoms (like changes in mood, cramps, heavy bleeding, etc.) impose additional burdens on women beyond health, affecting work performance due to absenteeism and presenteeism (Cook & Van Den Hoek, 2023; Schoep et al., 2019; Yáñez-Sarmiento et al., 2024). The literature also discusses pregnant women, who sometimes go to work despite health considerations suggesting otherwise (Gatrell, 2011).

There is evidence that women tend to use more sick days to care for family members (children, the elderly). Consequently, some women eventually feel they cannot afford to take sick days when they themselves are unwell (Lovell, 2004). A report published by the Israeli Civil Service Commission in 2015 found that women are absent from work more than men (40 days compared to 31). In the case of men, 51% of absences were due to vacation compared to 40% among women; 43% of female absences were due to illness or child sickness compared to 31% among men (Civil Service Commission, 2015).

In another study conducted among general practitioners in outpatient services, higher presenteeism was found among women, and the reasons for presenteeism varied between men and women (Gustafsson Sendén et al., 2016). The justifications for going to work while sick that received higher support among women compared to men included concern that patients would not receive treatment in case of absence, creating a workload for colleagues, and fear of an accumulation of work. Men, on the other hand, more frequently mentioned their ability to cope with the illness and economic reasons.

6 See on the [Hadassah University Medical Center website](#).

Another study suggests that men's pain threshold is higher than women's, despite the common perception to the contrary. This complex explanation involves physiological differences between men and women, behavioral differences (such as pain-coping techniques like distraction, openness, and social support), and cultural-social perceptions (e.g., the expectation that men will report pain less than women or differences among various ethnic groups) (Bartley & Fillingim, 2013). Therefore, men may be less inclined to admit to pain, whereas women may be better able to cope with it.

In conclusion, these factors should be considered when discussing gender differences in the context of absenteeism and presenteeism.

Income from work: The relationship between income from work and presenteeism is unclear. Presenteeism rates among low-income earners are expected to be higher, as these individuals are likely to experience greater financial harm than high-income earners — for example, when the workplace does not cover health-related absences from the first day of absence (Hansen & Andersen, 2008).⁷ On the other hand, among high-income earners, there is a high proportion of managers and employees in managerial roles. The significant responsibility of these roles, along with high financial compensation, is often accompanied by long working hours, both on-site and off-site. Work overload may push managers and employees in managerial positions to come to work even when unwell.

Organizational culture⁸ and workplace relationships: It is known that managers influence employee morale, and job satisfaction can affect behavior and performance (Bleikh, 2023). Manager behavior can also influence presenteeism and absenteeism in organizations. Many managers advocate coming to work even when they are not well, thereby setting an example for their employees (Baker-McCleary et al., 2010). Managers can also affect the stress levels of employees by creating a competitive culture where employees are expected to work long hours without considering that this may lead to increased presenteeism (Prater & Smith, 2011).⁹

7 Data from the Social Survey shows that the percentage of employees aged 25–64 who receive full pay for sick days starting from the first day increases with income.

8 A very common definition of organizational culture is: “the way things are done around here.” See Deal & Kennedy, 1982.

9 According to the literature, long working hours are associated with sleep problems (Choi et al., 2020). Impaired sleep quality causes fatigue, which in turn can lead to negative outcomes such as health issues, workplace accidents, absenteeism, and presenteeism (Swanson et al., 2011). Another study found that employees with insomnia tended towards more absenteeism and presenteeism compared to employees without insomnia (Hwang et al., 2022).

Poor relations between an employee and their supervisor can create mental stress that may affect the employee's health (changes in blood pressure, emotional disturbances, metabolic issues). Organizationally, this can manifest as an increase in absenteeism but also as an increase in presenteeism caused by work-related stress (Gilbreath & Karimi, 2012). It can be assumed that managers who maintain close relationships with their employees are more likely to recommend that they should stay home if they don't feel well. Such messages from managers can help reduce presenteeism among employees.

Several arguments can be found regarding the impact of peer relationships on presenteeism. In a workplace that promotes a culture of mutual assistance, some employees may avoid taking a sick day to avoid overloading their colleagues with tasks (McKevitt et al., 1997). This behavior can contribute to increased presenteeism. On the other hand, one could argue that if there is a culture of concern for colleagues' health in the workplace, sick employees may prefer to take time off, thus reducing presenteeism. Additionally, the practical possibility of temporarily replacing a sick employee (ease of replacement) can mitigate the phenomenon of presenteeism.

Stress factors: Many employees experience a certain level of stress and tension, which may stem from events at the workplace, personal life, or a combination of both. Workplace stress can arise, for example, from a heavy workload or activities under strict timelines. Personal life stress can be related, for instance, to financial pressure, manifesting in an individual's ongoing inability to provide for basic needs such as food, clothing, healthcare, and family leisure activities (Peirce et al., 1996), or to economic uncertainty, financial losses, and the inability to make ends meet (Shah et al., 2012). Among stress factors, one can also include ongoing feelings of job insecurity.¹⁰ This prolonged state of mind may have health and behavioral impacts. In a situation of job insecurity, employees may come to work despite illness to demonstrate their indispensability and avoid job loss (Kim et al., 2020; Kinman & Grant, 2021).

Finally, it is well-known that chronic stress can harm an individual's health and performance in the labor market. A prolonged state of mental stress can impact health, leading, for instance, to feelings of depression, extreme fatigue,

10 The term *job insecurity* in its broad sense includes concerns about several scenarios: losing one's job, a decrease in *status* at work, uncertainty regarding the future, and, in particular, a decline in the employee's confidence in their ability to find a new job. (De Witte, 1999).

headaches, increased blood pressure, and the development of feelings of anxiety (American Psychological Association, 2011; Salleh, 2008). Therefore, it can be expected that the impact of stress factors on an employee's health may lead to situations where individuals feel conflicted between going to work while ill or staying home.

Negative behavior in the workplace: Mental stress among employees can result from negative behavior from managers and colleagues, such as bullying, harassment, or a sense of unfairness (Sanderson & Cocker, 2013). A toxic workplace environment may lead to feelings of fear, anxiety, harm to general health, and depression, as well as a reduction in the employee's commitment to their workplace and a desire to leave it (Di Martino et al., 2003; Rogers & Kelloway, 1997). Employees who feel discriminated against may feel compelled to come to work even when sick out of concern for their status and job. Among employees who feel depressed, there is a greater tendency to go to work despite their condition, partly because depression is perceived as a condition that does not justify absence (Johns, 2010).

Autonomy: Job autonomy has a positive association with employee well-being. However, the relationship between autonomy and presenteeism is unclear. Employees with high autonomy may be more likely to come to work while sick because they can take their foot off the pedal — in other words, work fewer hours, reduce their work pace, or take on less demanding tasks. This flexibility, or the employee's ability to adjust their schedule and work pace when ill (adjustment latitude), means managers consciously allow employees to come to work when sick with the understanding that their productivity may decrease. This approach could be seen as an alternative to medical absence, which results in a complete drop in productivity. On the other hand, high autonomy may reduce rates of presenteeism, for instance, because workplace flexibility and potentially the employee's status allow them more easily to take a break from work when sick (Ashby & Mahdon, 2010; Johansson et al., 2015; Johansson & Lundberg, 2004; Johns, 2010).

Work-family and family-work conflict: Sometimes, job requirements conflict with family demands, and other times, family demands affect an individual's performance at work. Johns (2011) describes the rationale underlying the relationship between these variables. The work-family conflict may have a positive relationship with presenteeism. The idea is that job demands may interfere with family functioning, thus pushing people to come to work

regardless of their health condition. Conversely, the family-work conflict may reduce presenteeism. The pressure from home demands may lead to more absenteeism from work, thereby reducing the tendency to come to work when ill. However, an alternative perspective on Johns' last argument is that family-work conflict could increase presenteeism among some employees. Frequent absences due to family demands may be perceived negatively at work, prompting individuals to come to work occasionally even when sick. For other employees, the burden of demands at home may lead them to escape to work even when ill. Thus, this is an empirical issue that requires in-depth examination.

Presenteeism in Israel: Findings from the multivariate analysis

To obtain more accurate estimates regarding the direct effects of independent variables on the probability of presenteeism, a multivariate analysis was conducted.¹¹ The dependent variable is assigned a value of 1 if the respondent reported coming to work while sick, and a value of 0 if they did not. The following analysis focuses solely on salaried employees, as most of the independent variables available in the database pertain exclusively to this group. However, it is worth noting that presenteeism rates are higher among the self-employed compared to salaried employees (74% versus 65%). The results of the multivariate analysis are presented in Appendix Table 2, which also includes separate models for men and women. Additionally, to assess the sensitivity of the results, further estimates were conducted for ordinary salaried workers (employees without authority to hire or promote others) and for salaried employees without chronic health issues.¹² Examining the latter group allows for a focus on employees who encounter health situations in the gray area — illnesses that may prompt the individual to decide whether to stay home or go to work. The independent variables are divided into several main groups: socio-demographic characteristics, health condition characteristics, employment characteristics, and workplace relationships.

11 For a detailed discussion of the methodological issues, see the Appendix.

12 Employee groups excluded from this analysis include those with chronic health issues lasting more than six months that interfere with daily functioning; employees who were absent for medical reasons for more than 15 days during the year; and employees whose general health condition is typically "not so good" or "not good at all."

Figure 2 shows the expected rates of presenteeism by gender, sector (Jews, Arabs, Druze, etc.), religiosity level, and education level.¹³ The findings indicate that, after controlling for other characteristics, presenteeism is expected to be higher among women (with a gap of 8 percentage points). As noted, women tend to use more sick days and child sick leave, which contributes to increased absenteeism and thus may encourage presenteeism.¹⁴ The multivariate analysis controlled for a range of health variables. Health conditions more common among women (like migraines) or unique to women (menstruation-related symptoms, pregnancy) may also contribute to an increase in presenteeism among them. Failure to account for specific health issues can partially explain the difference in presenteeism between women and men. For some women, absence from work involves a burden on colleagues or clients and an accumulation of work, which may also contribute to increased presenteeism among them.

Expected presenteeism rates are highest among the religious and Haredi (ultra-Orthodox Jewish) populations compared to other groups, a finding that persisted across all estimates except for men. Among the Arab population, presenteeism rates are the lowest, even in separate estimates for ordinary employees. These findings may reflect cultural differences in how groups from different backgrounds view working while ill, and may also indicate a concern among some employees that their absences will be perceived negatively by employers.

Academic education does not affect presenteeism, as was also found in separate estimates within subgroups.

13 Additional demographic variables considered in the regression include the individual's age, the number of children in the household, and marital status.

14 In the Social Survey 2016, there was a question examining the primary reason for choosing part-time employment. Among salaried employees aged 25–64, about one-fifth of women, compared to approximately 4% of men, responded that their choice of part-time work was due to caring for children, a family member, or managing the household.

Figure 2. Expected presenteeism rates among employees aged 25–64, by socio-demographic characteristics

Notes: The sample includes salaried employees who were sick at some point during the year and does not include employees who worked from home. The expected rates are based on the multivariate analysis (Appendix Table 2). The horizontal lines at the end of the bars represent the 95% confidence intervals.

Source: Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Social Survey 2016

Figure 3 presents expected presenteeism rates according to the health characteristics of individuals available in the database. The figure indicates that the vast majority of these characteristics are not correlated with presenteeism. Presenteeism rates are expected to be significantly lower among employees who required prescription medication (a gap of 5 percentage points). This relationship was found in all estimates except for women. Additionally, presenteeism is expected to increase as employees report more frequent worries that interfere with sleep. This relationship is more pronounced among men, ordinary employees, and employees without chronic health conditions. It is possible, of course, that more specific variables related to employees' medical issues, along with variables examining lifestyle characteristics (such as smoking, alcohol consumption, diet, and physical activity), would provide a more comprehensive picture of the relationship between health characteristics and presenteeism.

Figure 3. Expected presenteeism rates among employees aged 25–64, by health characteristics

Notes: The sample includes salaried employees who were sick at some point during the year and does not include employees who worked from home. The expected rates are based on the multivariate analysis (Appendix Table 2). The horizontal lines at the end of the bars represent the 95% confidence intervals.

Source: Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Social Survey 2016

Figure 4 presents expected presenteeism rates by employment characteristics. Higher presenteeism is expected among employees with managerial authority. In separate estimates by gender, this trend was found among men but not among women. Presenteeism is expected to be high among those working over 50 hours per week (a gap of 9–10 percentage points compared to those with fewer work hours). This correlation also holds for ordinary employees and employees without chronic health conditions but does not persist in the breakdown by gender. Across all estimates, there was no significant effect of

the supervisor's gender on presenteeism rates. Higher presenteeism rates are expected to be among employees whose counterparts in similar roles are primarily women. This finding holds across all estimates except for ordinary employees. In the estimate for men, higher presenteeism rates are expected to be among employees with no peers in similar roles.

Working during leisure hours is associated with higher presenteeism rates. The gap in presenteeism between those who work during leisure time infrequently or not at all and those who work frequently during leisure time ranges around 7–10 percentage points. This correlation mainly holds in estimates for ordinary employees and men and may be related to workaholism, which could drive employees to go to work even when sick.¹⁵

An increase in the level of work challenge is associated with higher rates of presenteeism. This finding holds across all estimates, except among women.

The study examined two aspects that indicate the degree of job autonomy: control over task order and control over work pace. The data show that presenteeism rates are expected to be significantly higher among employees who have control over the order of tasks compared to those who do not have such control (a gap of 6 percentage points). This correlation is observed across all estimates except for men. It is possible that some employees come to work while ill due to their ability to reprioritize tasks (for example, performing less demanding tasks). Additionally, employees who have control over task order may perceive their work as highly important, which could increase their tendency to go to work when sick. On the other hand, control over the pace of work was found to have no effect on presenteeism in any of the estimates.

Finally, the data also indicate that working under strict deadlines is expected to increase presenteeism. Similar results are obtained in separate estimates for women and ordinary employees.

15 A study conducted among white-collar workers in an Italian company found that an increase in the level of work addiction was associated with higher rates of presenteeism (Mazzetti et al., 2019).

Figure 4. Expected presenteeism rates among employees aged 25-64, by employment characteristics

Notes: The sample includes salaried employees who were sick at some point during the year and does not include employees who worked from home. The expected rates are based on the multivariate analysis (Appendix Table 2). The horizontal lines at the end of the bars represent the 95% confidence intervals.

Source: Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Social Survey 2016

Figure 5 presents expected presenteeism rates within a group of variables examining workplace relationships. An increase in the frequency of managerial support and assistance was found to reduce presenteeism. Presenteeism rates among employees who frequently receive support from their managers are expected to be lower by about 7–10 percentage points compared to those who do not receive such frequent support. This result holds across the entire sample of salaried employees and within distinct groups, suggesting the importance of leadership culture in organizational health culture regarding employee well-being.

A toxic work environment, exemplified by exposure to violent behavior, can negatively affect an employee's mental and overall health.¹⁶ Presenteeism rates were examined in this context, and the data show that presenteeism is expected to be more common among employees exposed to violent behavior at the workplace compared to those not exposed (a gap of 10 percentage points). This relationship is observed across all estimates except for women. Presenteeism rates are also higher among salaried employees who felt discriminated against compared to those who did not (a gap of 5 percentage points).¹⁷ This association holds in separate estimates for ordinary employees and employees without chronic health conditions.

16 Violent behavior includes physical or verbal violence, threats, humiliation, bullying, or sexual harassment. Among the population of salaried employees in the research, some 14% reported being exposed at least to one of such behaviors.

17 The study examined whether individuals felt discriminated against based on age, nationality, ethnicity or origin, religion or belief, gender, sexual orientation, physical or mental disability, or skin color. Among the population of salaried employees in the research, some 10% reported being exposed at least to one of such behaviors.

Figure 5. Expected presenteeism rates among employees aged 25–64, by workplace relationships

Notes: The sample includes salaried employees who were sick at some point during the year and does not include employees who worked from home. The expected rates are based on the multivariate analysis (Appendix Table 2). The horizontal lines at the end of the bars represent the 95% confidence intervals.

Source: Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Social Survey 2016

In addition to the findings presented so far, further analysis revealed several more insights:

1. When job demands interfere with family functioning (work-family conflict), there is a greater tendency to come to work while sick. This relationship is consistent across all estimates but is more significant among women. Conversely, family-work conflict was not found to have an effect on presenteeism in any of the estimates.
2. Job insecurity was not found to have an impact on presenteeism across all estimates.

3. Among employees who reported that they would continue working even if their financial situation allowed them not to work, the expected presenteeism rates are higher compared to employees who responded negatively to this question. This relationship exists among men but not among women.
4. Income does not affect presenteeism rates among salaried employees. In the estimate for women, a weak positive effect of income was found, while no effect was observed among men.
5. There is no correlation between medical absences and presenteeism.¹⁸

The conclusions derived from the estimates of models for ordinary salaried workers and salaried workers without chronic health conditions are generally similar to those from the model for all salaried employees (Appendix Table 2).

In the breakdown by economic sectors (Figure 6), presenteeism is expected to be more prevalent among employees in accommodation and food services, local administration, public administration and defense, and education (with expected presenteeism rates of at least 70%). In contrast, employees in transportation and postal services have the lowest expected presenteeism rates (57%).

18 The causal relationship between these two variables is complex, and the explanation for this is provided in the methodological appendix.

Figure 6. Expected presenteeism rates among employees aged 25–64, by economic sector

Notes: The sample includes salaried employees who were sick at some point during the year and does not include employees who worked from home. The expected rates are based on the multivariate analysis (Appendix Table 2). The horizontal lines at the end of the bars represent the 95% confidence intervals.

Source: Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Social Survey 2016

It is worth focusing on the education sector, which, even after controlling for independent variables, is characterized by high rates of presenteeism. This sector accounts for the highest proportion of employees — approximately 15% of all salaried employees aged 25–64 and about 23% of salaried women. In this sector, there is significant interpersonal interaction between educational staff and students, which could impact public health if employees come to work while suffering from contagious illnesses.

A look at the State Ombudsman's report sheds light on the reasons for the high rates of presenteeism in the education sector (State Ombudsman, 2019). The report highlights a number of points: (a) from 2010–2018, the average absence rate from total teaching hours was about 14%; (b) in 2017–2018, approximately 40% of total absence hours were without a substitute; (c) the absence rate from

total annual working days among teachers was 5.6%, which was higher than the absence rate of employees in other sectors and also higher than teachers in other countries.

The report uses strong language to emphasize the significant implications of teachers' absences:

The absence of teaching staff from their positions in the education system can have serious consequences, including potential harm to the quality of teaching, the functioning of the school, and the students, as well as affecting students' motivation and academic achievement. Additionally, absences cause direct and indirect damage, including the need for the Ministry of Education ... to allocate time and resources to arrange replacements for regular teaching staff, as well as the economic cost associated with hiring substitutes (State Ombudsman, 2019, p. 1086).

These insights highlight a structural issue in the education system, one possible outcome of which could be increased presence among teaching staff.

Summary

This study described the extent of presenteeism in Israel and examined its influencing factors. It analyzed data from the period before the Covid-19 pandemic, based on the Social Survey 2016 by the Central Bureau of Statistics, which included a wide range of questions about employees' working conditions.

It is important to note that presenteeism rates in Israel are high in the pre-Covid-19 period — about 60% of workers in Israel reported going to work while sick. According to the literature review, during the same period, presenteeism rates in European Union countries averaged 42%, while in the US it was 68%.

Research literature indicates that presenteeism has both health and economic costs. On the health side, presenteeism can be a significant source of spreading infectious diseases. The term breaking the chain of infection, which became prominent in public discourse during Covid-19, might be relevant to other contagious illnesses as well. It can be assumed that today, after the Covid-19 crisis, there is greater awareness that sick individuals risk infecting those they come into contact with. At the same time, in certain non-contagious health conditions, presenteeism allows the employee to maintain a professional and

social routine, which may aid in recovery. On the economic side, presenteeism incurs costs due to decreased productivity, increased professional errors, and safety violations. Moreover, under certain health conditions, coming to work while sick can worsen an individual's health, leading to increased absenteeism later. The costs of presenteeism are challenging to assess compared to those associated with medical absences, although some studies suggest that the costs of presenteeism are higher than those of absenteeism.

The study focused on salaried employees aged 25–64 and yielded several findings. Among women, presenteeism rates were higher than among men, even after accounting for a wide range of variables, including job characteristics. It is possible that the differences in presenteeism between men and women stem from factors that could not be identified in the current study due to data limitations. These factors have been discussed in the literature review. For example, the gender gap in presenteeism may partly be attributed to the tendency of women to take more sick days and family-related illness days, which contributes to an increase in absences and may encourage presenteeism at some point. Health conditions unique to women and health issues more common among women may also contribute to an increase in presenteeism among them.

The research identified differences between men and women in job characteristics influencing presenteeism. For instance, control over task order increases presenteeism only among women, whereas job challenge has a strong positive effect on presenteeism only among men. Work-family conflict (when job demands interfere with family functioning) has a positive effect on presenteeism, however it is more prominent among women.

The study supports the argument for the importance of organizational culture, particularly the influence of managerial leadership, in addressing presenteeism. Employees who regularly receive support from managers exhibit lower presenteeism rates than those who do not. It can also be assumed that managers who maintain close relationships with their employees are more likely to recommend that they stay home if unwell. Therefore, organizations, especially in industries with high levels of interpersonal interaction, should develop a supportive managerial culture, as it plays a critical role in reducing the phenomenon of presenteeism. This will not only contribute to improving employee well-being within the organization but may also yield economic benefits for the organization.

In the education sector, presenteeism rates are among the highest, even after accounting for other variables. Presenteeism in the education sector — the largest economic sector, employing about 15% of salaried workers — may impact public health when employees are sick with contagious diseases, among other reasons, due to the high level of interpersonal interaction between teaching staff and students. Moreover, the high cost of teacher absences, as noted by the State Ombudsman — affecting both the school and students (disrupting school functioning and making it challenging to find substitutes at short notice, alongside reduced student motivation and academic achievement) — could at least partially explain the high rates of presenteeism in the education system.

Finally, we note that in light of the growing understanding of the phenomenon of presenteeism, especially after the Covid-19 pandemic, there is a need to create a high-quality, updated database and conduct more comprehensive research to address this issue.

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Appendix

Methodology

This section explains in detail the choice of estimation method. The main points are as follows:

Simultaneity: The central equation in the study examines the relationship between presenteeism and a variety of independent variables (such as socio-demographic characteristics and job characteristics). The variable that examines whether an individual is absent for medical reasons involves a simultaneity problem between the two variables — just as medical absences can influence presenteeism, the reverse may also occur.¹⁹ Empirically, this constitutes a system of two simultaneous equations.

$$PRS = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X_1 + \alpha_2 ABS + e_1$$

$$ABS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_2 + \beta_2 PRS + e_2$$

PRS - presenteeism; ABS - medical absence

X_1 - the group of independent variables in the presenteeism equation

X_2 - the group of independent variables in the medical absenteeism equation

e - error terms

The rationale for using a system of simultaneous equations is that each equation has meaning independently of the others (Wooldridge, 2012). For example, it makes sense to have a model in which medical absenteeism appears as an independent variable for presenteeism. In a separate model where medical absenteeism is the dependent variable, it would also be reasonable to include presenteeism as an independent variable.

19 Sometimes, choosing absenteeism can be an alternative to presenteeism. In this case, an increase in absenteeism reduces presenteeism. For others, absenteeism may increase presenteeism, for example, when an individual feels uncomfortable about frequent absences. Conversely, presenteeism can influence absenteeism. For instance, delaying treatment for an illness at an early stage can worsen the health condition and lead to increased future absences. For certain individuals, choosing presenteeism can serve as an alternative to absenteeism, thus increasing presenteeism can serve as an alternative to absenteeism, thereby reducing absences.

One possible solution to the simultaneity problem is a two-stage estimation of Probit models (Madhala, 1983, p. 246). In the first stage, the medical absenteeism equation is estimated, including all exogenous variables from equations 1 and 2. The medical absenteeism equation should contain at least one independent variable that is not included in the presenteeism equation. The independent variable included in the medical absenteeism equation but not in the presenteeism equation is the need for medical treatment. According to the analysis, this variable does not affect presenteeism but does influence medical absenteeism (Appendix Table 1). This is therefore a reduced-form equation.

In the second stage, the expected probability of medical absenteeism is calculated. In the third stage, the presenteeism equation is estimated, including the expected probability of medical absenteeism from the second stage as an independent variable: $PRS = \delta_0 + \delta_1 X_1 + \delta_2 ABS^* + e$ where the asterisk indicates the expected value of the variable.

Appendix Table 1. Multivariate analysis: Medical absences and presenteeism, among salaried employees aged 25–64, reduced-form equations

	Absenteeism salaried workers	Presenteeism salaried workers	Absenteeism women	Presenteeism women	Absenteeism men	Presenteeism men	Absenteeism ordinary workers	Presenteeism ordinary workers	Absenteeism w/o workers with persistent health problems	Presenteeism w/o workers with persistent health problems
In need of medical care	0.457***	0.0205	0.412***	-0.07	0.592***	0.107	0.447***	0.032	0.376***	0.0245
Other variables	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Constant	-0.507	-1.600***	-0.0589	-1.341***	-0.576	-1.675***	-0.652*	-1.793***	-0.611*	-1.254***
Number of observations	2,852	2,852	1,463	1,463	1,389	1,389	2,241	2,241	2,284	2,284
Pseudo R ²	0.122	0.139	0.143	0.179	0.187	0.182	0.134	0.144	0.113	0.138

Note: This table includes variable that affects the probability of medical absence but do not impact presenteeism. The remaining variables in this table are identical to those reported in Appendix Table 2.

Significance levels: *p < 0.10; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

Source: Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Social Survey 2016

Appendix Table 2. Multivariate analysis: Presenteeism among salaried employees, aged 25–64

	Salaried employees	Women	Men	Ordinary employees	Employees without persistent health problems
Women	0.259***			0.241***	0.211**
Population group (Reference category: Secular)					
Traditional, not so religious	0.0513	0.106	0.012	0.111	0.080
Traditional, religious	-0.005	0.104	-0.123	0.086	0.083
Religious	0.238**	0.164	0.352**	0.295**	0.252*
Haredim	0.398**	0.209	0.836***	0.447***	0.345**
Non-religious Arabs	-0.316**	-0.299	-0.248	-0.276*	-0.351**
Religious Arabs	-0.290**	-0.365*	-0.209	-0.294**	-0.230
Married	-0.035	-0.054	-0.083	-0.010	-0.020
Number of children	0.004	-0.069	0.086	0.004	0.030
Number of children squared	-0.001	0.013	-0.016	-0.004	-0.005
Has an academic degree	-0.107	-0.158	-0.145	-0.042	-0.082
General health (Reference category: Excellent)					
Good	-0.016	0.136	-0.185*	-0.041	-0.033
Not so good, not at all good	0.005	0.098	-0.204	-0.020	
Persistent health problems (Reference category: None)					
Has: Do not interfere in daily life	-0.041	-0.140	-0.022	0.037	-0.021
Has: They interfere in daily life	-0.002	0.054	-0.047	-0.069	
Has severe functional disability	-0.031	-0.302	0.136	-0.077	
Requires prescription medications	-0.164**	0.014	-0.246**	-0.203**	-0.160**
Feelings of depression (Reference category: Never)					
Rarely	-0.008	0.038	0.014	-0.059	0.017
Always, sometimes, or occasionally	-0.064	0.035	-0.087	-0.019	-0.061
Worries that interfere with sleep (Reference category: Never)					
Rarely	0.047	0.126	-0.039	0.078	0.059
Sometimes, occasionally	0.199**	0.102	0.283**	0.194**	0.191**
Always, frequently	0.235**	0.186	0.210	0.187	0.225*

Appendix Table 2 (continued). Multivariate analysis: Presenteeism among salaried employees, aged 25–64

	Salaried employees	Women	Men	Ordinary employees	Employees without persistent health problems
Feelings of stress (Reference category: Never)					
Rarely	-0.074	-0.003	-0.079	-0.138	-0.113
Sometimes, occasionally	-0.089	-0.056	-0.140	-0.091	-0.110
Always, frequently	-0.061	-0.034	-0.130	-0.114	-0.060
Has managerial responsibilities	0.195**	0.146	0.305***		0.191**
Employment position (Reference category: Part-time, up to 34 hours)					
Full-time (35-49 hours)	0.054	-0.069	-0.125	0.005	-0.014
Over full-time (50 hours or more)	0.330***	0.105	0.246	0.262**	0.276**
Shift worker	-0.047	-0.088	0.018	-0.032	-0.034
Works at more than 1 place	0.059	-0.188	0.136	0.079	0.008
Direct supervisor is female	0.031	0.054	0.025	0.010	-0.028
Number of workers at same level (Reference category: Same number of men and women)					
Mostly men	0.009	0.220	-0.028	-0.047	-0.009
Mostly women	0.184**	0.236**	0.287*	0.157	0.212**
Job is unique to the individual	0.010	-0.039	0.360**	-0.013	-0.026
Sick pay from first day of illness	-0.100	0.017	-0.223**	-0.091	-0.099
Work during free time to complete tasks (Reference category: Rarely, never)					
Once, twice a month	0.209***	0.307**	0.133	0.228**	0.159*
Once, twice a week	0.207**	0.107	0.261**	0.250**	0.217**
Almost daily	0.306**	0.245	0.368**	0.342**	0.201
Rigid time frame for work (Reference category: Never)					
Sometimes, rarely	-0.201**	-0.187	-0.245*	-0.310***	-0.285***
About half of the time	0.039	0.082	-0.025	0.128	0.033
Most of the time	0.155*	0.226*	0.007	0.211**	0.123
All the time	0.168*	0.456***	-0.111	0.178*	0.156
Has control of work flow	0.064	-0.241	0.182	0.015	0.013

Appendix Table 2 (continued). Multivariate analysis: Presenteeism among salaried employees, aged 25–64

	Salaried employees	Women	Men	Ordinary employees	Employees without persistent health problems
Has control of task flow	0.186**	0.544***	-0.016	0.243**	0.238**
Challenging work (Reference category: No)					
Little challenge	0.300**	0.059	0.777***	0.321**	0.209
Some challenge	0.350***	0.145	0.650***	0.352***	0.292**
Highly challenging	0.439***	0.173	0.835***	0.421***	0.400***
Peer support (Reference category: Rarely, never)					
Sometimes, occasionally	0.050	0.194	0.06374	0.021	0.151
Always, frequently	0.053	0.156	0.098	0.032	0.135
Supervisory support (Reference category: Rarely, never)					
Sometimes, occasionally	-0.100	-0.253	-0.096	-0.060	-0.156
Always, frequently	-0.299***	-0.452***	-0.354**	-0.267**	-0.355***
Exposed to violent behavior	0.354***	0.189	0.563***	0.381***	0.322***
Feels discrimination	0.170*	0.121	0.201	0.223*	0.264**
Fear of losing job (Reference category: No fear)					
Little fear	0.084	0.063	0.087	0.013	0.048
Very, greatly fearful	0.119	0.123	0.194	0.145	-0.070
Ability to cover expenditures (Reference category: Succeed with no difficulty)					
Succeed	0.102	0.073	0.137	0.162	0.105
Not so successful, Not at all	0.119	0.127	-0.011	0.179	0.147
Difficulty functioning with family due to work responsibilities (Reference category: Never)					
Rarely	0.104	0.072	0.206	0.154	0.073
Sometimes, occasionally	0.327***	0.454***	0.319**	0.347***	0.380***
Frequently	0.460***	0.722***	0.329**	0.496***	0.492***
Difficulty functioning at work due to family responsibilities (Reference category: Never)					
Rarely	0.008	0.080	0.020	-0.021	-0.001
Occasionally, sometimes, frequently	-0.073	-0.053	-0.103	-0.085	-0.116
Prefer to work even if finances do not require it	0.148**	-0.000	0.333***	0.171**	0.098

Appendix Table 2 (continued). Multivariate analysis: Presenteeism among salaried employees, aged 25–64

	Salaried employees	Women	Men	Ordinary employees	Employees without persistent health problems
Salary (Reference category: Up to NIS4,000)					
NIS4,001 to NIS5,000	-0.046	0.005	0.049	0.039	-0.186
NIS5,001 to NIS6,000	0.027	0.138	0.297	0.0447	-0.023
NIS6,001 to NIS7,500	0.181	0.244	0.470*	0.201	0.050
NIS7,501 to NIS10,000	0.079	0.190	0.292	0.137	-0.034
NIS10,001 to NIS14,000	0.217	0.597***	0.302	0.243	0.132
NIS14,001 to NIS21,000	0.206	0.575**	0.199	0.099	0.17
Over NIS21,000	0.139	0.532*	0.191	0.047	0.014
Likelihood of being absent due to medical reasons	0.251	-0.708	0.564	0.501	0.101
Other control variables	+	+	+	+	+
Constant	-1.685***	-0.991*	-1.850***	-1.939***	-1.283***
Number of observations	2,852	1,463	1,389	2,241	2,284
Pseudo R²	0.139	0.179	0.182	0.144	0.138

Notes: Some variable categories are grouped due to sample size. The probability of medical absences is based on the expected value calculated from the absenteeism equation in the first stage and included as an independent variable in the presenteeism equation. The job challenge variable is constructed from the sum of three questions (yes/no; 0/1): Does your job involve a learning process? Solving complex problems? Solving unexpected problems? A higher score indicates a greater level of job challenge for the individual. Additional control variables include economic sector, occupation, type of employment contract, tenure at the workplace, workplace size, residential region, and individual's age.

Significance levels: *p < 0.10; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

Source: Haim Bleikh, Taub Center | Data: CBS, Social Survey 2016

Questions from the Social Survey 2016 by the Central Bureau of Statistics

In the past twelve months, did you work while you were sick?

Responses: Yes, No

What is your general health status?

Responses: Very good, Good, Not so good, Not good at all

Do you have any health or physical problem? Meaning a problem that has existed for six months or more.

Responses: Yes, No

Does this problem interfere with your daily activities?

Responses: Interferes a lot, Interferes, Does not interfere much, Does not interfere at all

In the past twelve months, did you need prescription medication?

Responses: Yes, No

In the past twelve months, did you need medical treatment?

Responses: Yes, No

In the past twelve months, did you feel stressed?

Responses: Always or often, Sometimes or occasionally, Rarely, Never

In the past twelve months, did you feel depressed?

Responses: Always or often, Sometimes or occasionally, Rarely, Never

In the past twelve months, did worries interfere with your sleep?

Responses: Always or often, Sometimes or occasionally, Rarely, Never

Do you have difficulty walking or climbing stairs?

Responses: No difficulty, Slight difficulty, Great difficulty, Cannot at all

Do you have difficulty dressing or bathing?

Responses: No difficulty, Slight difficulty, Great difficulty, Cannot at all

Do you have difficulty remembering or concentrating?

Responses: No difficulty, Slight difficulty, Great difficulty, Cannot at all

Do you have difficulty seeing? (even when wearing glasses)

Responses: No difficulty, Slight difficulty, Great difficulty, Cannot see at all

Do you have difficulty hearing? (even when using a hearing aid)

Responses: No difficulty, Slight difficulty, Great difficulty, Cannot hear at all

In general, does your job involve solving unexpected problems on your own?

Responses: Yes, No

In general, does your job involve complex tasks?

Responses: Yes, No

In general, does your job involve learning new things?

Responses: Yes, No

Your co-workers help and support you

Responses: Always or often, Sometimes or occasionally, Rarely, Never, Question not relevant

Your manager helps and supports you

Responses: Always or often, Sometimes or occasionally, Rarely, Never, Question not relevant

In this workplace, do you have managerial authority? (meaning the ability to promote or dismiss people)

Responses: Yes, No

Is your direct manager a man or a woman?

Responses: Man, Woman, No direct manager

The workers in a position similar to yours in the workplace are:

Responses: Mostly men, Mostly women, About equal numbers of men and women, Only you have this position

Do you fear that you might lose your job in the coming year?

Responses: Not at all, Slight fear, Great fear, Very great fear

In the past twelve months, did you struggle to fulfill family responsibilities due to work commitments?

Responses: Often, Sometimes or occasionally, Rarely, Never

In the past twelve months, did you struggle to fulfill work commitments due to family responsibilities?

Responses: Often, Sometimes or occasionally, Rarely, Never

Do you have control over the order of your tasks?

Responses: Yes, No

Do you have control over your work speed or pace?

Responses: Yes, No

In the past twelve months, how often did you work during your free time to meet work demands?

Responses: Almost every day, Once or twice a week, Once or twice a month, Less often, Never

Do you manage to cover all your household's monthly expenses, such as food, electricity, and phone bills?

Responses: Easily, Manage, Struggle somewhat, Do not manage at all

In the past twelve months, did you experience discrimination at work due to your age?

Responses: Yes, No

In the past twelve months, did you experience discrimination at work due to your nationality?

Responses: Yes, No

In the past twelve months, did you experience discrimination at work due to your ethnicity or origin?

Responses: Yes, No

In the past twelve months, did you experience discrimination at work due to your religion or belief?

Responses: Yes, No

In the past twelve months, did you experience discrimination at work due to your gender?

Responses: Yes, No

In the past twelve months, did you experience discrimination at work due to your sexual orientation?

Responses: Yes, No

In the past twelve months, did you experience discrimination at work due to a physical or mental disability?

Responses: Yes, No

In the past twelve months, did you experience discrimination at work due to your skin color?

Responses: Yes, No

In the past month, have you experienced verbal violence at your workplace?

Responses: Yes, No

In the past month, have you experienced unwanted sexual attention at your workplace?

Responses: Yes, No

In the past month, have you experienced threats or humiliating behavior at your workplace?

Responses: Yes, No

In the past twelve months, have you experienced physical violence at your workplace?

Responses: Yes, No

In the past twelve months, have you experienced bullying or harassment at your workplace?

Responses: Yes, No

In the past twelve months, have you experienced sexual harassment at your workplace?

Responses: Yes, No

If you could afford not to work financially, would you still work?

Responses: Yes, No